

DIGITAL LEARNING MATERIAL IN 2D ANIMATION FOR FIRST YEAR DRAFTING TECHNOLOGY STUDENTS

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Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation for First Year Drafting Technology Students

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Abstract

This study developed and evaluated a digital learning material in 2D Animation for First Year Drafting Technology Students of the Marikina Polytechnic College for the academic year 2023-2024. The developed digital learning material in 2D Animation was evaluated by two (2) groups of respondents composed of fifteen (15) experts and fifteen (15) industry practitioners. A survey questionnaire was utilized to gather the data, and it covered the following variables: quality of content and technical aspects. The findings revealed that the two groups of respondents evaluated the developed digital learning material in 2D Animation as Highly Acceptable with respect to quality of content with a grand weighted mean of 3.83 and 3.69, respectively. In terms of technical aspects, it gained grand weighted means of 3.88 and 3.76, respectively. In addition, there was no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed digital learning material in 2D Animation in terms of quality of content with a computed t value of 1.76, 1.12, 1.85, 0.98, 1.16, and 1.79, respectively. In terms of technical aspects, it gained a computed t value of 1.26, 1.37, 1.27, and 0.72, respectively. The insightful comments and suggestions provided by both groups of respondents hold significant potential for enhancing the quality and effectiveness of the developed digital learning material in 2D Animation. Furthermore, it was recommended that the School Administrators may encourage Instructors in other fields of specialization to explore on developing instructional materials that will help facilitate learning and improve the performance of their respective students.

Keywords: *digital, learning material, 2D animation, drafting technology*

Introduction

The animation industry is becoming more well-known around the world. The creativity, uniqueness, and skill of the local Filipino painters are highly regarded. The nation has been offering its animation services to the global community for over three decades. Because of this, one of the most vibrant and rapidly growing sectors in the nation is the animation business.

There is a considerable need for animators for projects that call for them, but the supply of qualified animators cannot keep up with the demands of the business. As of March 13, 2018, the ACPI reported that the number of Filipino animators in the Philippines had reached 6,000. The majority of them work in visual effects, advertising, and film outsourcing.

Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA), a government organization that includes animation in training and certification programs, has responded to this concern. President Fidel V. Ramos signed Republic Act No. 7996 into law in 1994, establishing the TESDA. The purpose of this law is to promote full participation and mobilization of the private sector, labor unions, local governments, and technical-vocational training institutions in the national human resource skills development process. Numerous courses, including 2D and 3D animation courses and vocational training in multimedia, animation, graphics, and game development, are available for free or at a reduced cost on TESDA. These courses can help individuals advance their knowledge and abilities in a particular field. (August 07, 2018)

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) has released many directives aimed at generating competent graduates in specific fields. One such directive is CHED Memorandum Order (CMO) No. 43 Series of 2008. CMO 43, sec. 2008, which attempts to guarantee that all graduates of the Technical-Vocational Education and Training (TVET) program must successfully complete the necessary TESDA proficiency exam in order to be eligible to get a National Certificate (NC), which is granted to those who satisfy the competency requirements.

At the time of this writing, Drafting Technology is one of the specializations available at Marikina Polytechnic College, proposed new policies, standards, and guidelines (PSG) for the Bachelor of Industrial Technology (BIT) program. The proposed PSG includes subject-specific courses that are expressly tailored to educate students on the basic skills needed to succeed in today's employment market. According to CMO no. 13, Series of 2023, a nation's ability to advance depends critically on having a skilled and informed workforce in industrial technology. Prioritizing sustainable development, boosting global competitiveness, and accelerating economic growth should be the top priorities of the national human resource framework. Colleges and universities like Marikina Polytechnic College are essential in preparing students for careers in technical knowledge, management, research, and entrepreneurship in the manufacturing and production industries. As such, it is essential to set strict guidelines outlining the goals, elements, and methods of execution of industrial technology programs.

As one progresses toward modern art, references and instructional materials such as learning materials, particularly in 2D Animation, both in digitalized and comprehensive hard copy forms, would be of great help and support for drafting students and instructors at the aforementioned college institution.

In this matter, the researcher conducted this study to develop a viable solution, keeping the following objectives in mind; to provide excellent and relevant education, assist instructors, particularly those teaching drawing and animating skills, and to provide alternative learning materials to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills in the field of 2D animation.

Research Questions

This study aimed to develop and evaluate Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation for First Year Drafting Technology Students of Bachelor of Industrial Technology of the Marikina Polytechnic College for the academic year 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What were the selected topics in Visual Graphics 2 as perceived by the Drafting Technology Instructors based on the TESDA Training Regulations for 2D Animation that were developed into digital learning material?
2. What was the evaluation of the experts and industry practitioners on the developed digital learning material in 2D Animation based on the following variables:
 - 1.1. Quality of Content
 - 1.1.1. Introduction
 - 1.1.2. Learning Objectives
 - 1.1.3. Lesson Content
 - 1.1.4. Assessments
 - 1.1.5. Job Sheets
 - 1.1.6. Rubrics
 - 1.2. Technical Aspects
 - 1.2.1. Layout and design
 - 1.2.2. ease of use
 - 1.2.3. graphics
 - 1.2.4. audio
3. Was there a significant difference between the evaluation of the two groups of respondents in terms of the above-mentioned variables?
4. 4. What were the comments and suggestions offered by the two groups of respondents to further improve the developed digital learning material in 2D Animation?

Literature Review

According to Kapur (2020), “Teaching-Learning Materials: Significant in Facilitating the Teaching-Learning Processes” shows that an essential tool that teachers utilize to transfer knowledge to their students is the teaching-learning materials (TLMs). Although it is well known that the primary purpose of TLMs is to support instructors as they teach lessons to students, with today's student-centered learning approach, learning materials also need to help students focus and develop their independent comprehension skills.

Additionally, “Theoretical Models for Teaching and Research” authored by Joy Egbert and Mary Roe (2020) includes a wide range of viewpoints and theoretical models that offer insightful information on the conception, use, and efficacy of virtual learning environments. The Community of Inquiry (CoI) framework is a well-known concept that has been debated. It highlights the significance of social, cognitive, and teaching presence in promoting meaningful online learning experiences. This approach emphasizes that critical thinking, teamwork, and knowledge production in virtual environments can only be promoted via the interaction of learners, instructors, and material.

Walters (2022) provided an explanation that digital learning, or e-learning, offers numerous benefits for education and training. Firstly, online learning provides Accessibility and Flexibility, allowing learners to access information on different devices at their convenience, overcoming geographical and time limitations. This adaptability improves engagement and caters to a wide range of learning preferences.

One of the linked studies that were examined was carried out by Bonifacio (2023) studied “Competency-based learning module in basic 3D Structural modeling for second year drafting technology students”. The study indicates that the five (5) topics that can be developed into a CBLM for 3D Structural modeling are footing, column, stairs, wall footing, and slab and beam. Furthermore, the average weighted means demonstrate that both sets of respondents strongly agree (SA) relative to content, completeness, organization, usefulness, and layout and design.

Likewise, the study “Printed and digitalized learning packets in Shoe pattern making for footwear and leathersgoods designing and processing course” by Dellomas (2023) found that it is necessary to produce and develop a learning packet that includes a guide and resources for the Specialize track of the curriculum at Marikina Polytechnic College.

Also, In the study "Development and Evaluation of Learning Materials in Specialized Subject of Journalism" conducted by Tutor (2020). The research seeks to provide educational material for the specialized field of journalism. The learning aspects were evaluated using criteria such as clarity, comprehensibility, creativity, and usability. The data showed that the instructor respondents highly agreed

with the aforementioned criterion.

Sirait et al. (2023) undertook a study entitled “The Development of Animation-Based Learning on Students’ Numeracy Literacy Skills,” which focuses on creating animation-based learning media to enhance numeracy within an autonomous curriculum program. Expert validation indicates a high level of validity, with a 90% average accuracy rate. Moreover, 93% of students and 90% of teachers rated the animation-based learning material as effective and useful, respectively. Notably, students who utilized the animation-based learning materials scored an average of 94% in the “very effective” category on numeracy literacy tests, suggesting animation's efficacy as a practical and successful learning medium for fourth-grade elementary school fractions.

Furthermore, the study by Daradar (2022) entitled “Animated Instructional Medium in Structural Foundation” indicates that teaching complex courses, concepts, and subjects, especially in the field of Structural Foundation, can pose challenges when using conventional instructional techniques such as static slides. When it comes to instructing pupils on these topics, animation is a transformative tool as it provides a visual approach to learning without directly showing the actual representation of the underlying structure.

Lastly, another study that could be linked to the current study was written by Okoli et. al. (2022) entitled “Effects of Computer Graphics and Animation Instructional Modes on Secondary School Students’ Achievement and Retention in Genetics,” which identified a consistent trend of subpar academic achievement and difficulty retaining lessons among students. This highlights the potential of multimedia technologies in improving educational outcomes, encouraging biology educators to use such graphics into their instruction to enhance performance and retention of knowledge.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized the quantitative-descriptive research methodology. Various authors of books and articles provide differing definitions of descriptive research.

Sirisilla (2023) states that descriptive research seeks to outline and define the phenomena in question. Bhat (2024) defined descriptive research as a research methodology that aims to elucidate the characteristics of the population or subject being investigated. This technique focuses on the “what” aspect of the research subject, rather than the “why” aspect.

Respondents

The sources of data in this research were the fifteen (15) experts, specifically, Drafting Technology Instructors with master’s degrees and/or Trainers’ Methodology Certificate Holders. Then, fifteen (15) industry practitioners composed of eight (8) TESDA Trainers, and seven (7) industry practitioners who are well-versed in animation.

Instrument

The researcher employed a survey questionnaire that was validated by two (2) language instructors and one (1) professional education instructor, this serves as the primary tool to collect evaluations from expert respondents and industry practitioners, and the instrument content was evaluated by selected experts and instructors.

Procedure

A survey checklist of topics in Visual Graphics 2 was administered to 10 Drafting Technology Instructors to identify the five (5) topics to be included in the digital learning material in 2D Animation based on the TESDA Training Regulation for 2D Animation, the topics included were identified by ranking based on data gathered from the survey checklist. Following the selection of subjects for inclusion in the learning material, video lessons were created using animation software, especially Adobe Animate, and a website was created to provide a much more comprehensive and detailed explanation of 2D Animation, a printed copy was also provided for those who opted to use a tangible material.

Before conducting the evaluation on the respondents, the survey questionnaire checklist was validated by a professional education instructor and two language instructors.

The researcher obtained permission from Marikina Polytechnic College, other Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), Division Office of Marikina, TESDA PaMaMariSan, and the creative industry sector to conduct her research. To evaluate the developed digital learning material, respondents were given a survey questionnaire checklist which comprised of two variables and 10 criteria.

To ensure the validity of the data collection tools, the researcher personally distributed and retrieved the questionnaires.

Ethical Considerations

To comply with the Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012, pertaining to the gathering of information to the respondents, it is indicated on the questionnaires that:

The protection of the respondents’ privacy will be secured.

The gathered information will only be used on the purpose of study and no other else.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings according to the study's research questions.

Selected Topics in Visual Graphics 2 as Perceived by the Drafting Technology Instructors that Can Be Developed into Digital Learning Material Based on the TESDA Training Regulation for 2D Animation

Table 1. *Selected topics in Visual Graphics 2 as perceived by the Drafting Technology Instructors that can be developed into a Learning Material based on the TESDA Training Regulation for 2D Animation*

Topics	f	Rank
Animation Theory and Fundamentals	8	3
Drawing Concepts and Techniques	7	4
Color Theory and Techniques	5	5
Adobe Animate User Interface	9	2
4 Adobe Animate Basics	10	1

The result of the conducted survey revealed that the lesson on (1) Four Adobe Animate Basics garnered the highest number of selections and ranked as the first topic. The following lessons were ranked second, third, fourth, and fifth ranks respectively: (2) Adobe Animate User Interface, (3) Animation Theory and Fundamentals, (4) Drawing Concepts and Techniques, (5) Color Theory and Techniques. The lessons taken into consideration in the development of the digital learning material in 2D Animation were the aforementioned topics.

Evaluation of the Experts and Industry Practitioner- Respondents on the Developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation

Table 2. *Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation in Terms of Introduction under Quality of Content*

The introduction...	Respondents			
	Experts		Industry Practitioners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. is clear.	3.73	HA	3.73	HA
2. makes the target learner interested in the topic.	3.73	HA	3.60	HA
3. makes use of language and explanations that can be easily understood by both students and instructors.	3.87	HA	3.73	HA
4. is concise.	3.87	HA	3.53	HA
5. communicates the main idea of the statement.	3.93	HA	3.67	HA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.83	HA	3.65	HA
Standard Deviation	0.29		0.25	

It can be seen in Table 2 that both the Experts and Industry Practitioners agree that the developed learning material in terms of the Quality of Content in Introduction is highly acceptable with an overall weighted mean of 3.83 and 3.65, respectively. This implies that the level of accuracy and reliability of the information presented in the introduction should be taken into account when developing educational materials. According to Shahab, et. al. (2020), research has demonstrated that the organization of textbooks and learning materials, namely the introductory portion, has a substantial influence on students' motivation to study.

Table 3. *Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation in Terms of Learning Objectives under Quality of Content*

The learning objectives...	Respondents			
	Experts		Industry Practitioners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. are communicated effectively to guide the learning process.	3.87	HA	3.60	HA
2. are appropriate to the learner's level.	3.80	HA	3.67	HA
3. are relevant to the educational needs of both instructors and students.	3.87	HA	3.87	HA
4. provide the necessary direction of what the learners will learn.	3.80	HA	3.53	HA
5. are presented in a SMART way.	3.73	HA	3.80	HA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.81	HA	3.69	HA
Standard Deviation	0.33		0.26	

It can be gleaned in Table 3 that the Experts and Industry Practitioners- respondents shows that the developed digital learning material are highly acceptable and is communicated effectively; appropriate to the learner's level; relevant to the needs of the learner and instructors; has a precise direction on what the students will learn; and most of all it is presented in a SMART way, making it having

an overall weighted mean of 3.81 and 3.69, respectively.

The initial phase of the course design process involves defining the aims and goals of the subject, as stated in an article released by Boston College-CTE Resources (2023). An effective learning/instructional material design should be precise and comprehensive, providing students with clear expectations for the session and outlining how their performance will be evaluated.

Table 4. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation in terms of Lesson Content under Quality of Content

	<i>The lesson content...</i>	<i>Respondents</i>			
		<i>Experts</i>		<i>Industry Practitioners</i>	
		<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	is presented in a clear and understandable manner.	4.00	HA	3.60	HA
2.	effectively facilitates the application of knowledge and skills.	3.87	HA	3.67	HA
3.	presents ideas that are congruent to the learning objectives.	3.93	HA	3.80	HA
4.	is appropriate to the learner's level.	3.80	HA	3.60	HA
5.	contains relevant information about 2D Animation.	3.87	HA	3.67	HA
Overall Weighted Mean		3.89	HA	3.67	HA
Standard Deviation		0.34		0.31	

This indicates that the lesson content in the developed learning material in 2D Animation is coherent and comprehensible, effectively supports the application of knowledge and skills, aligns well with the learning objectives, matches the learners' proficiency level, and provides pertinent information regarding 2D Animation, with an overall weighted mean of 3.89 and 3.67, respectively, and verbally interpreted as highly acceptable.

In Yasay's (2023) study, the same criterion was employed. The statement suggests that the quality of lesson content, characterized by its organization, level of information, and clarity, significantly influences the effectiveness of the learning material as a whole.

Table 5. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation in Terms of Assessments under Quality of Content

	<i>The assessments...</i>	<i>Respondents</i>			
		<i>Experts</i>		<i>Industry Practitioners</i>	
		<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	and instructions presented in each lesson are understandable and clear.	3.80	HA	3.60	HA
2.	are relevant and congruent to the learning objectives.	3.87	HA	3.87	HA
3.	are a good tool to measure the students learning.	3.87	HA	3.67	HA
4.	are presented in a simple to complex questions.	3.73	HA	3.80	HA
5.	provide necessary directions of what the learners will do.	3.87	HA	3.80	HA
Overall Weighted Mean		3.83	HA	3.75	HA
Standard Deviation		0.23		0.22	

It can be gleaned from the statistical data presented above that the two groups of respondents shows that the developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation is highly acceptable and has valid, reliable, and understandable assessments that are congruent with the learning objectives; a good tool to measure the students learning; and are presented in a simple to complex questions; and it provides necessary directions of what the learners need to accomplish, which result on having an overall weighted mean of 3.83 and 3.75, respectively. This aligns with Olipas' (2023) study, which emphasizes the significance of assessments in the educational process, especially when utilizing learning modules. Assessments are widely recognized as an effective method for evaluating students acquired knowledge.

Table 6. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation as to Quality of Content in Job Sheets

	<i>The Job sheets...</i>	<i>Respondents</i>			
		<i>Experts</i>		<i>Industry Practitioners</i>	
		<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	are effective in supporting the learning objectives.	3.80	HA	3.53	HA
2.	engage interaction and promote students to be skilled-oriented.	3.80	HA	3.87	HA
3.	are an effective tool for assessing the students' abilities.	3.73	HA	3.73	HA
4.	are relevant to the student's competency.	3.73	HA	3.60	HA
5.	are provided with necessary directions on what the students need to do.	3.87	HA	3.60	HA
Overall Weighted Mean		3.79	HA	3.67	HA
Standard Deviation		0.31		0.26	

It can be seen in the table presented below that the Experts and Industry Practitioners – respondents observed that the developed Digital

Learning Material in 2D Animation presented Job Sheets that are aligned with the learning objectives; and encouraged students interaction to be skilled-oriented; an effective tool to evaluate the students' abilities; relevant to the students level; and are provided with enough directions on what the students need to do. Which come up with a descriptive rating of highly acceptable with an overall weighted mean of 3.79 and 3.67, respectively. Parallel to this is an article authored by Triyanto, Parno and Sukatiman (2022), assert that job sheets play a vital role as instructional resources that facilitate project-based learning.

Table 7. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation in Terms of Rubrics under Quality of Content

The rubrics...	Respondents			
	Experts		Industry Practitioners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. are provided in all Job sheets.	3.87	HA	3.73	HA
2. effectively communicate the criteria for assessment.	3.87	HA	3.60	HA
3. are aligned with the stated learning objectives.	3.80	HA	3.80	HA
4. are relevant to measure the learner's competency.	3.87	HA	3.67	HA
5. can effectively measure the knowledge learn.	3.87	HA	3.60	HA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.85	HA	3.68	HA
Standard Deviation	0.24		0.27	

Table 7 shows that the two groups of respondents agrees that the developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation is highly acceptable in terms of its rubrics under quality of content, with an overall weighted mean of 3.85 and 3.68, respectively. This clearly demonstrates that the developed Digital Learning Material for 2D Animation has successfully integrated rubrics that adeptly communicate the assessment criteria, ensuring seamless alignment with the stated learning objectives. In line with this, in an article authored by WhiteHorse (2024), Rubrics are just as important as job sheets because they may evaluate and analyze students' acquired knowledge and skills. Utilizing rubrics provides advantages for both students and instructors.

Table 8. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation in Terms of Layout and Design under Technical Aspects

	Respondents			
	Experts		Industry Practitioners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The layout and design are visually appealing and relevant to the subject.	3.93	HA	3.73	HA
2. The illustrations and pictures presented in the video tutorial and the printed learning material are of a size that can be clearly seen.	3.93	HA	3.80	HA
3. The entire design and layout stimulate student attention and create coherence.	3.87	HA	3.87	HA
4. The graphical presentation enhances learning.	3.87	HA	3.73	HA
5. The layout and position of each content are understandable.	3.87	HA	3.60	HA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.89	HA	3.75	HA
Standard Deviation	0.26		0.37	

It can be gleaned from the table presented that the Expert and Industry Practitioners- respondents both evaluated the developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation in terms of Layout and Design with a descriptive rating of highly acceptable with an overall weighted mean of 3.89 and 3.75, respectively. This implies that a well-constructed visual material shows a great impact on the students learning making this criterion deemed to be important to consider when developing a learning material. Malla (2023), used the same variable to evaluate the CBLM. Both of the two groups of respondents observed that the variable mentioned is presented and well-constructed which makes the developed learning material look appealing and can gain interest from the reader.

Table 9. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation in Terms of Ease of Use under Technical Aspects

	Respondents			
	DT Experts		Industry Practitioners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The learning material and video tutorial can be accessed in many ways.	3.80	HA	3.73	HA
2. The learning material and video tutorial are uploaded digitally and can be accessed anywhere.	3.93	HA	3.80	HA
3. The learning material are accessible to the learners through android phones, desktop, and laptop.	3.93	HA	3.73	HA
4. The video tutorial can be access through scanning the QR codes.	3.93	HA	3.87	HA

5. The video tutorial can be viewed through the use of the application provided on the learning material.	3.93	HA	3.73	HA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.91	HA	3.77	HA
Standard Deviation	0.21		0.31	

It can be seen from Table 9 that the Experts and Industry Practitioners- respondents evaluated the developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation in terms of Ease of Use with a descriptive rating of highly acceptable with an overall weighted means of 3.91 and 3.77, respectively. The findings clearly show that the developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation can be accessed and used in a variety of ways; it is uploaded digitally and can be accessed anywhere.

Muralidhar (2024) emphasizes the significance of using QR Codes and Augmented Reality in education and communication to enhance the learning experiences of students and educators.

Table 10. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation in Terms of Graphics under Technical Aspects

	Respondents			
	Experts		Industry Practitioners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The graphics are easy to interpret and comprehend in relation to the video tutorial content.	3.87	HA	3.87	HA
2. The visual elements enhance the overall engagement with the video tutorial.	3.93	HA	3.80	HA
3. The graphics are relevant and supportive of the lesson content in the video tutorial.	3.87	HA	3.67	HA
4. The learning material observes proper mechanics such as capitalization, punctuations, and spelling.	3.87	HA	3.73	HA
5. The visual content of the learning material and video tutorial are clear and understandable.	3.93	HA	3.73	HA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.89	HA	3.76	HA
Standard Deviation	0.27		0.30	

It can be observed in Table 10 that both groups of respondents observed that the developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation has shown good construction and implied the design principles in terms of the Technical Aspects specifically in the use of graphics, both on the video tutorials embedded on the learning material, and the digital learning material itself which makes the digital learning material in 2D Animation highly acceptable. This clearly implies that the developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation has graphics that are easy to interpret and comprehend in relation to the video tutorial content

Kuba (2021) emphasizes the crucial significance of high-quality graphics in educational resources for students. The analysis emphasizes the impact of educational materials that are thoughtfully developed with visual features, which can greatly improve understanding, promote the transfer of knowledge, and increase motivation among learners.

Table 11. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation in Terms of Audio under Technical Aspects

	Respondents			
	Experts		Industry Practitioners	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The audio in the video tutorial complements the visual content and supports the learning objectives.	3.80	HA	3.87	HA
2. There were no issues with the accessibility or consistency of the audio throughout the video tutorial.	3.80	HA	3.67	HA
3. The audio enhanced the overall presentation of the lesson content and provides interest to the students.	3.87	HA	3.73	HA
4. The background music on the video tutorial doesn't overpower the words/lines mentioned.	3.80	HA	3.67	HA
5. The words on the video tutorial are clear and comprehensible.	3.87	HA	3.80	HA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.83	HA	3.75	HA
Standard Deviation	0.32		0.29	

The statistical data from Table 11, reflects that both Experts and Industry Practitioner- respondents agree that the developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation is highly acceptable and has provided video tutorials that have quality and understandable audio as well as language, resulting with an overall weighted mean of 3.83 and 3.75, respectively.

Umayam (2024) highlighted the advantages of high-quality audio in education and videos, as it can enhance the whole learning experience. Video learning is purported to enhance motivation, facilitate deeper learning, and enhance retention.

Significant Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation

Table 12. Summary of Test of Difference in the Evaluation of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation in terms of Quality of Content

criteria	experts		industry practitioners		computed t value	decision	interpretation
	owm	s	owm	s			
1. introduction	3.83	0.29	3.65	0.25	1.76	fail to reject the h0	not significant
2. learning objectives	3.81	0.33	3.69	0.26	1.12	fail to reject the h0	not significant
3. lesson content	3.89	0.34	3.67	0.31	1.85	fail to reject the h0	not significant
4. assessments	3.83	0.23	3.75	0.22	0.98	fail to reject the h0	not significant
5. job sheets	3.79	0.31	3.67	0.26	1.16	fail to reject the h0	not significant
6. rubrics	3.85	0.24	3.68	0.27	1.79	fail to reject the h0	not significant

According to the findings detailed in Table 12, the assessment of the Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation by both Experts and Industry Practitioners reveals a consistency across various parameters including Introduction, Learning Objectives, Lesson Content, Assessments, Job Sheets, and Rubrics, particularly within the dimension of Quality of Content. The computed t-values, upon comparison with the critical t-value (2.05), indicate a lack of significant variance, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Consequently, it can be inferred that the perceptions of the respondents exhibit a degree of uniformity, suggesting a consensus regarding the evaluated aspects of the developed material.

Table 13. Summary of Test of Difference in the Evaluation of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation in Terms of Technical Aspects

Criteria	Experts		Industry Practitioners		Computed t Value	Decision	Interpretation
	OWM	s	OWM	s			
1. Layout and Design	3.89	0.26	3.75	0.37	1.26	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
2. Ease of Use	3.91	0.21	3.77	0.31	1.37	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
3. Graphics	3.89	0.27	3.76	0.30	1.27	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
4. Audio	3.83	0.32	3.75	0.29	0.72	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant

Table 13 reflected that the computed t value is less than the critical t value (2.05) resulting in the decision to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, this concludes that the respondents' evaluations do not vary significantly.

This supports that the Experts and Industry Practitioner- respondents agrees that the following criteria: Layout and Design, Ease of Use, Graphics, and Audio were highly accepted and was evidently observed in the developed Learning Material in 2D Animation.

Comments and Suggestions Offered by the Two Groups of Respondents to Further Improve the Developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation

Comments. Listed below are the comments mentioned by the evaluators on the developed digital learning material in 2D Animation. Quality of Content

- It is a very interesting module to use. We need more of this.
- In evaluating the 2D Animation module, I appreciate its clarity and accuracy in presenting technical concept.
- Very well-written learning material for 2D Animation!
- The use of both traditional and digital learning material is engaging and promotes innovation in the course mentioned.
- This is a good reference for an aspiring animator. The topics and terms being used was easy to understand, good utilization of the modern way of accessing the files as well as for the choice of software used, Adobe products are known widely since it can be access for free. Good job! Hoping to see more learning items or modules for animation, since we only have few.

Technical Aspects

- Very good layout and design! Fresh ideas were evident.
- The overall design and layout of the learning module display creativity. Visual contents are sufficient in every lesson and assessment activities are congruent to the lesson content.
- Excellent! This learning material can surely serve as a teaching and learning tool for 2D Animation especially with its creative and advanced features.
- The design and overall design context were impressive and easy to understand.
- I appreciate how you used the illustrations and visual content of the IM's. I enjoy the construction style overall.
- The content was excellent, this can really catch the attention of a learner who is seeking for knowledge on 2D animation, the graphics used was very creative and matches the concept of the subject.
- The video tutorial is very informative. Amazing skills on animation.

Suggestions. Listed below are the suggestions given by the evaluators on the developed learning material in 2D Animation.

- To elevate learning experience, I suggest enhancing interactivity, ensuring visual consistency, and keeping the content regularly updated to align with the industry trends.
- A higher contrasting color can highlight design elements.
- Overall, the module is very well researched, comprehensive, and the information is presented in an engaging way! Information is substantiated with appropriate visuals Points that can be improved: - Add Chapter Titles ex "Unit 1, Lesson 1: Concepts of 2D Animation" in the Table of Contents and the Navigation Bar in the Google Sites so that students may navigate more efficiently and find what topic they are looking for.
- As much as possible condense and summarize the text. Most students who are interested in visual arts and animation learn a lot through images than massive paragraphs compared to other students who are ore academically interested.

Conclusions

Based on the result of the study, the researcher concluded the following: The developed Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation is highly acceptable by the two groups of respondents in terms of Quality of Content and Technical Aspects. The group of Experts and Industry Practitioner- respondents have the same views about the given variables in the Digital Learning Material in 2D Animation. The insightful comments and suggestions provided by both groups of respondents hold significant potential for enhancing the quality and effectiveness of the developed digital learning material in 2D Animation.

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